

EVIDENCE-BASED
TOXICOLOGY

Evaluation Report (Round 2) for **TEBT-2025-0007**

Submission information table

Submission Title	Using directed acyclic graphs to assess collider and confounding bias in reviews of observational studies: an example using the impact of residential exposure to animal feeding operations on human health
Submission Reference	TEBT-2025-0007
Handling Editor	Paul Whaley 0000-0003-4021-0785 ▾
Editor Declaration Of Conflicting Interests	The handling editor has, to the best of their knowledge, no conflicts of interest that would compromise their decision-making on this submission.
Number of Reviewers	1 editor and 3 peer-reviewers
Submission Type	Research Article ▾
Preregistration Level	N/A (Not Applicable) ▾ (explanation)
Preprint DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14955069
Evaluation Round	Round 3 ▾
Evaluation Stage	Acceptance Note ▾
Evaluation Date	17 Mar 2026
Use of AI in evaluation	DataSeer.ai was used to perform data availability checks on the manuscript.

Recommendation

Accept ▾

Editor's Summary of Reviewer Comments

Written by the Handling Editor as a summary of the key points from the peer-review process

In this manuscript, the authors assess how directed acyclic graphs (DAGs) can help researchers evaluate observational studies for confounding and inappropriate control of collider variables.

The broad concept of writing a paper to help researchers use DAGs was very well-received by the reviewers. However, the reviewers had general questions about how well the authors' approach to presenting and analysing their DAG aligned with best practices, the validity of modifying an existing DAG against creating a new DAG when assessing causality in a systematic review, and specific questions about the validity of some of the authors' judgements in creating the modified DAG on which they base their analysis.

The authors made comprehensive revisions to their manuscript in response to the reviewer comments, and I am satisfied based on feedback from one reviewer and my own reading of the manuscript that the reviewers' comments have been sufficiently addressed. One reviewer did suggest adding further discussion; however, given that this manuscript has been through two rounds of extensive revision already, and what the additional discussion ought to cover is not fully clear to me, I am happy to accept this manuscript for publication with no further revisions.

Acceptance Note

This manuscript was accepted for publication by the handling editor Paul Whaley after 1 round of editorial evaluation and 1 round of peer-review evaluation. The evaluation reports for the manuscript can be found at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15178178>. Preprint versions of the manuscript and author responses to comments in the evaluation reports can be found at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14955069>.